

**Let the
dialogue
begin**

D6.3 WEBSITE

Project: **Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management**

Acronym: **Firelogue**

Document Information

Grant Agreement Number	101036534	Acronym	FIRELOGUE
Full Title	Cross-sector dialogue for Wildfire Risk Management		
Start Date	01/11/2021	Duration	48 months
Project URL	https://Firelogue.eu/		
Deliverable	D6.3 Website		
Work Package	WP6 Dissemination and Insights Upscaling		
Date of Delivery	Contractual	M6	Actual M6
Nature	Report	Dissemination Level	Public
Lead Beneficiary	EDGE		
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Document History

Version	Issue Date	Stage	Description	Contributor
V_0.1	12/04/2022	Draft	Draft for Review	Katrina Petersen (TRI) Jorge Gomes (VOST) Dimitris Maragos (NOA)
V_0.2	30/04/2022	Final	Format changes. Annex added. Minor text changes in the website.	Sofia Economou (EDGE)

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
IAs	Innovation Action(s)
WFRM	Wildfire risk management

Executive Summary

The main scope of the Firelogue website is to disseminate information and raise awareness of the project's goals, activities, and foreseen actions, allowing the different types of users to navigate smoothly and accurately across the various sections.

The primary intention and goal are to reflect our project's mission and brand identity to our website. Grab visitor's attention, provoke action and give them a reason to stay within the first few seconds.

This report provides a short description of the content and structure of the Firelogue website.

1 Introduction

The website serves as the primary gateway to all information, news and updates related to the various project activities. It has already been designed in a modern, professional, and attractive way, allowing visitors / users to navigate across the various webpages easily and quickly. Several dynamic and static items have been foreseen to ensure a good balance of visual appeal and professional outlook.

The front-end consists of a number of distinctive and dynamic content parts, which are positioned accordingly to accommodate the content of each section. Furthermore, it will provide up to date information on project events and link to social media accounts ([Twitter](#), [Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), and [Instagram](#)).

2 Content

The main elements included are:

Logo & Header, Main Menu: It is a burger multi-level menu (Figure 7), consisting of the following main menu entries and sub-menus: Home, Innovation Actions, Communication Booster, Outreach, Partners, News, FAQs, Contact Us.

The Firelogue website (firelogue.eu) is designed to act as the main information gateway informing the user community (incl. the public) and stakeholders of the Firelogue objectives and goals, thematic areas, current and planned activities, and outputs/achievements, partnering organisations and services of the IAs.

2.1 Home Page

The users navigate to the different pages of the website through a number of static and dynamic items presented in the homepage. The following sections have been implemented:

- The motto of the Project and a “fire image”, also the menu up right and the logo up left (Figure 1)
- As the users scroll down, they find the description of Firelogue project (Figure 2)
- And after that, the goal, values, and mission of the project (Figure 3)
- Below the users find a small description of the Key WFRM Projects and their logos (Figure 4)
- The 3 latest news are displayed (Figure 5)
- A calendar for the events is placed under the news which containing all the main WFRM events and also events curated by Firelogue (Figure 6)
- Clickable footer provides an additional route to access the various sections of the website (Figure 17)

The homepage is a chance to attract visitors on our site and learn more about Firelogue and its' services. The "Home" page is designed in a way that conveys the majority of information needed. It's the first thing visitors will see, and it can serve as a short "elevator pitch" letting the visitor know what Firelogue site all is about. So, our website introduction content absolutely needs to be compelling.

Figure 1: Home Page – First Page

Figure 2: Home Page – Firelogue Description

Figure 3: Home Page – Goal Mission/Values

Figure 4: Home Page – IAs Description

Figure 5: Home Page - The 3 latest News

Figure 6: Home Page – Calendar

2.2 WFRM Key Projects

At the WFRM Key Projects Subpage, the user can find information about each Innovation Action ([DRYADS](#), [SILVANUS](#), [FIRE-RES](#)) (Figure 8), about the Precursor project ([FirEUrisk](#)) (Figure 9) and also about the Networks “<https://firelinks.eu>/Firelinks” and “[FIRE_IN](#)” and the DSS Platform “[SAFERS](#)”(Figure 11).

Also, this subpage provides information about the 3 phases of a wildfire event as described by the WildFire Risk Management These 3 phases describe the “Before” a wildfire event (Prevention and Preparedness), “During” a wildfire (Detection and Response) and “After” a wildfire (Restoration and Adaptation) and they refer to the categories that the IAs will give their solutions and technologies (Figure 10).

Figure 7: Home Page - Burger Menu

Figure 8: WFRM Key Projects' Page – Description

Figure 9: WFRM Key Projects' Page - 3 Phases Description

Figure 10: WFRM Key Projects' Page – Other Projects

2.3 Communication Booster

This page will contain information and the link about Firelogue’s platform “Communication Booster”. Some features of the platform will be ready in the next year and then this page will take its first form. You can find more about the Communication Booster in the Deliverable 6.4 User Engagement and Dissemination Strategy Tools & Set Up.

Figure 11: Communication Booster Page

2.4 Outreach

On this page the user will be able to find Firelogue's Communication Material like leaflets, posters, brochures, the logo, the deliverables of the brand identity and the brand manual.

Communication activities are central to the success and impact maximisation of Firelogue. Through a dedicated section on the website, the various different stakeholders will obtain information on the dissemination activities (conferences, workshops, scientific publications, etc.) carried out by the project.

Overall, this section is expected to maximise the visibility and impact of the project, through the efficient communication of the project's progress to the stakeholder community.

Figure 12: Outreach Page

2.5 Partners

Firelogue developed the Partners page by asking each partner to provide general information about them and also their role in Firelogue project.

Figure 13: Partners' Page – Logos and Descriptions

2.6 News

All the activity of the Firelogue project will be displayed under the News Section. Press releases and articles appearing in specialised magazines/journals and/or national media will be included too. Additionally, all the highlights of the project (e.g., upcoming events, news, activities) will be announced through this section along with the calendar at the “Home” page. This page will give more detailed information on announcements of workshops and special sessions in scientific conferences and meetings and announcements of activities open to the public (e.g., press conferences).

Figure 14: News Page – All News included here

2.7 Contact

This page will give to the visitors all the contact information of the project. A contact form will be available in order easily and fast to communicate with Firelogue team.

Figure 15: Contact Us form

2.8 Footer

A website footer provides site visitors with a sense of consistency, as the same information will appear at the bottom of every single one of your site pages. Due to evolving user behaviour, creating a sense of consistency is increasingly important.

To maintain visitor engagement, secondary site navigation is a must-have footer item (even if it duplicates our header menu) therefore, Informative and enticing information is included. A well-

crafted, cohesive website footer can have a greater impact on user engagement than any other area of our site.

Transparency and informing the public about how their data are being used are two basic goals of the GDPR. Firelogue website, will include a privacy notice template that will be adapted to the project.

Figure 16: Footer

2.9 Web Accessibility

We must always take into account all people for their proper information. This is why Firelogue's website has a Web Accessibility box for people with certain disabilities (such as low vision or colour disorders, etc.) according to the WCAG 2.0 standard. This box contains some features that will help people with certain disabilities to explore the website easier and at their convenience. The box is placed at the down-left site of the website.

Figure 17: Web Accessibility Box

Figure 18: Web Accessibility Box on the First Page

3 Foreseen Updated

At present, several of the planned functionalities have been implemented into the website.

The Firelogue website will be an environment that is dynamically refreshed and curated so that all external stakeholders can stay up-to-date with the latest developments, news, events, milestones, etc. of Firelogue.

In any case, the website is an ongoing process that will have to keep up with user demands and the communication team will constantly work into the on-going web strategy and support.

Click on <https://Firelogue.eu/> to see all the above content and be part of the Firelogue's community.

THIS IS THE END OF THIS DOCUMENT

THIS PROJECT HAS RECEIVED FUNDING FROM THE EUROPEAN UNION'S HORIZON 2020
RESEARCH AND INNOVATION PROGRAMME UNDER GRANT AGREEMENT NO 101036534